

Table 1. Average data from the best lines in the 1993 observational trial conducted in the coffee-growing area of Colombia, Naranjal Experimental Station, Risaralda.

Line	Panicles (no.)	Tillers (no.)	Grains		Sterile (%)	Quality traits ^a				Yield (t ha ⁻¹)
			Filled (no.)	Empty (no.)		GT	WB	GL	Disp	
CT10037-9-4-M-4-8P-1-M	113	141	376	123	33	I	0.2	L	4	4.4
CT6196-33-11-1-3-M	120	143	348	99	28	I	0.6	L	5	4.0
CT9997-5-3-M-4-M	120	135	345	136	39	IB	0.4	L	3.6	3.8
CT10069-27-3-1-4	132	160	526	66	12	IA	2	L	3.4	5.2
CT10037-9-7-M-1-M	120	155	512	176	34	I	0.2	L	5	5.6
CT10037-30-3-M-1-2P-2-M	116	124	433	78	18	I	0.2	EL	5	3.8

^aGT = gelatinization temperature, WB = white belly, GL = grain length, and Disp = dispersion.

Table 2. Yield ability, tiller number, and sterility percentage of the six breeding lines evaluated.^a Naranjal Experimental Station, Risaralda, Colombia. 1994.

Line	Yield (t ha ⁻¹)	Tillers (no.)	Filled grain (%)
CT10037-9-4-M-4-8P-1-M	3.6 bc	82.53 bc	81.9 a
CT6196-33-11-1-3-M	3.3 c	85.00 ab	81.0 a
CT9997-5-3-M-4-M	3.2 c	84.01 abc	58.0 b
CT10069-27-3-1-4	4.3 ab	88.13 ab	87.5 a
CT10037-9-7-M-1-M	4.7 a	90.85 a	83.0 a
CT10037-30-3-M-1-2P-2-M	3.2 c	76.05 c	82.5 a

^aMeans in a column followed by the same letter are not significantly different (P = 0.05) by DMRT.

conditions at 700 masl. Rainfall during the cropping season ranged from 128 mm in

March, the end of the growing season, to 394 mm in January.

CT10069-27-3-1-4 was selected in 1993 as one of the most promising lines, so agronomic evaluation was done. A simple unreplicated trial was conducted. Row planting produced a higher yield than spaced or hill planting, independent of the N level (0, 60 kg N ha⁻¹) and seed density (60, 80, 100 kg ha⁻¹). The rice responded to N at all densities, and the ideal seed density was 80 kg ha⁻¹ (data not shown).

The best six lines were evaluated again in 1994 in a yield trial in a randomized block design with three replications (Table 2). The yield potential of these lines was confirmed, with the highest yielding line (CT10037-9-7-M-1-M) averaging 4.7 t ha⁻¹, similar to that of CT10069-27-3-1-4 and statistically different from the four others.

These preliminary results indicate that CIAT upland breeding lines are an alternative for the coffee-growing region of Colombia. Further research will aim to identify the best line for release and suitable agronomic practices. ■

MTU9993, a promising rainfed upland rice for Andhra Pradesh, India

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MTU9993 is a high-yielding variety identified from the progeny of Rasi/Fine Gora (white) for the rainfed uplands of coastal Andhra Pradesh. It was released in 1993 to replace tall traditional varieties that are low yielding and prone to lodging. The short-duration (105-110 d) variety has straw-colored glumes and white kernels. MTU9993 is superior to the existing rainfed upland rice cultures, such as MTU17 and Mettasannavari, in grain quality and yield, shortness, tolerance for lodging, strong seed dormancy, tolerance for iron deficiency, and resistance to leaf blast.

The variety was tested from 1988 to 1992 and yielded 10-57% more than local checks (see table). ■

Performance of MTU9993 under rainfed upland conditions at multiple locations during dry seasons 1988-92.

Location and variety	Grain yield (t ha ⁻¹)				
	1988	1989	1990	1991	1992
<i>Chinthapally</i>					
MTU9993	3.2	3.5	-	-	-
MTU17 (check)	2.9	2.5	-	-	-
% increase	10.3	40.0	-	-	-
<i>Lam, Guntur</i>					
MTU9993	1.8	3.9	2.5	2.3	1.7
MS. Vari (check)	1.6	3.1	1.8	1.5	1.2
% increase	12.5	25.8	38.8	53.5	41.7
<i>Ragolu</i>					
MTU9993	4.4	3.4	-	2.7	2.8
MTU17 (check)	3.3	2.6	-	2.2	2.2
% increase	33.3	30.8	-	22.7	27.3
<i>Jagtial</i>					
MTU9993	0.9	2.6	2.2	-	-
Rasi (check)	0.8	2.2	2.0	-	-
% increase	12.5	18.2	10.0	-	-
<i>V.R. Gudem</i>					
MTU9993	2.3	2.2	1.8	1.4	-
MTU17 (check)	1.8	1.4	1.2	1.2	-
% increase	27.5	57.1	50.0	16.7	-
<i>Maruteru</i>					
MTU9993	4.3	2.5	2.2	2.8	-
MTU17 (check)	2.9	2.0	1.6	2.0	-
% increase	48.3	25.0	37.5	40.0	-